

From In Silico To In Vitro: Exploring Indole Derivatives For Dual-Target Parkinson Therapy

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ABSTRACT

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder and ranks as the second most common cause of neurodegeneration-related mortality worldwide. The continuous rise in PD incidence underscores the urgent need for novel, effective, and safe therapeutic strategies. In the present study, computer-aided drug design (CADD) methodologies, particularly structure-based virtual screening (SBVS), were employed to identify and optimize potential dual-target agents for PD management. Molecular docking studies were performed to investigate the binding orientations, interaction profiles, and affinities between designed ligands and their respective targets. The therapeutic focus involved the inhibition of monoamine oxidase-B (MAO-B) and activation of the dopamine D₂ receptor (D₂R), both of which play key roles in modulating dopaminergic neurotransmission. Based on published pharmacophoric data, structural features favorable for MAO-B inhibition and D₂R agonism were established. A virtual library of indole derivatives was then designed and computationally screened to identify compounds exhibiting dual activity. The docking experiments, conducted using crystallographic structures obtained from the Protein Data Bank (PDB), revealed promising indole scaffolds with significant binding affinity and interaction stability at both targets. This integrated computational workflow highlights the potential of indole-based compounds as dual-acting MAO-B inhibitors and D₂R agonists, providing valuable insights for the rational design of novel therapeutic agents for Parkinson's disease.

Keywords: Parkinson's disease · Indole derivatives · Computer-aided drug design (CADD) · Structure-based virtual screening (SBVS) · Monoamine oxidase-B (MAO-B) inhibitors · Dopamine D₂ receptor (D₂R) agonists · Molecular docking · Dual-target therapeutics

INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a prevalent and progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized by the selective loss of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpc), leading to a marked reduction in dopamine levels within the striatum. The depletion of dopamine disrupts the normal inhibitory control of striatal neurons, resulting

in impaired regulation of motor functions such as balance, coordination, and movement. Clinically, PD manifests through hallmark symptoms including tremors, bradykinesia, rigidity, and postural instability, and it remains the second most common neurodegenerative disorder after Alzheimer's disease[1][2][3]. Monoamine oxidase-B (MAO-B), an enzyme responsible for the oxidative deamination of dopamine, plays a significant role in the

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pathogenesis of PD. Elevated MAO-B activity in the brain contributes to increased oxidative stress and neuronal damage. Evidence suggests that selective inhibition of MAO-B can slow disease progression, alleviate symptoms, and improve dopaminergic neurotransmission. Consequently, MAO-B inhibitors such as selegiline and rasagiline have been widely used in PD therapy.[2]

In addition to MAO-B inhibition, direct activation of dopamine receptors represents another important therapeutic approach. Dopamine agonists act by mimicking the action of dopamine at its receptors, thereby compensating for its deficiency. Among these, the dopamine D₂ receptor (D₂R) is of particular interest, as it belongs to the G protein-coupled receptor (GPCR) superfamily—one of the most widely targeted protein families in drug discovery. Approximately 475 approved drugs act on 108 GPCR subtypes, with 65 of these targeting the dopamine receptor family. D₂-like receptors, in particular, play a pivotal role in regulating motor control, cognition, and emotional behavior, and their activation has shown beneficial effects in PD management[4][5].

The present study aims to design and identify novel anti-Parkinsonian agents capable of dual action—selective inhibition of the MAO-B enzyme and activation of the dopamine D₂ receptor. Utilizing computer-aided drug design (CADD) approaches, including structure-based virtual screening (SBVS) and molecular docking, indole derivatives were optimized to achieve favorable binding affinities toward both targets. This dual-target strategy seeks to enhance therapeutic efficacy while minimizing adverse effects, providing a rational framework for the development of multifunctional agents against Parkinson's disease.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For the present study, the three-dimensional crystal structures of human monoamine oxidase-B (MAO-B; PDB ID: 2V60) and the human dopamine D₂ receptor (D₂R; PDB ID: 6CM4) were retrieved from the Protein Data Bank (PDB, www.rcsb.org). A virtual library comprising 5 indole-based ligands was designed based on established pharmacophoric features relevant to MAO-B inhibition and D₂R agonism. The designed compounds were subjected to

molecular docking studies to predict their binding modes and affinities toward the active sites of both targets. Docking simulations were performed using the AutoDock 4.2 (version 1.5.6) software suite, following standard protocols for grid generation, ligand preparation, and receptor optimization. The resulting docked conformations were analyzed to evaluate key molecular interactions, binding orientations, and docking scores, providing insights into the potential dual-target activity of the designed indole derivatives.

PHARMACOPHORE MODELING

A pharmacophore represents the ensemble of steric and electronic features within a molecule that ensures optimal supramolecular interactions with a specific biological target, thereby eliciting a desired biological response. Pharmacophore modeling establishes a correlation between the biological activity of compounds and the three-dimensional spatial arrangement of key functional groups in a series of active analogues.

The principal pharmacophoric features considered during hypothesis generation include hydrogen bond acceptors (A), hydrogen bond donors (D), hydrophobic groups (H), positively ionizable (P) and negatively ionizable (N) functionalities, as well as aromatic ring systems (R). These features are defined according to well-established chemical structural patterns and are spatially organized within the ligand conformation to enable effective receptor binding.

Active ligands exhibiting an identical set of pharmacophoric features with comparable spatial arrangements were clustered to derive a common pharmacophore hypothesis (CPH). This hypothesis represents the shared molecular features essential for biological activity and serves as a guiding model for the rational design of novel ligands with enhanced affinity and selectivity toward the target proteins. The identified pharmacophoric model thus provides a robust framework for designing indole-based derivatives with potential dual activity against MAO-B and D₂R targets in Parkinson's disease.

LIGAND LIBRARY DESIGN

A virtual library comprising 5 novel lead molecules was constructed based on the structural insights obtained from the binding interactions between known ligands and the selected targets, MAO-B and D₂R. The design strategy incorporated the essential pharmacophoric features required for optimal biological activity, as identified in previously reported active analogues. Key chemical features, including hydrogen bond acceptors (HBA), hydrogen bond donors (HBD), and aromatic ring systems, were

utilized as screening criteria to guide the selection and optimization of potential ligands.

The designed compounds were generated to align with the common pharmacophore hypothesis (CPH) established for both targets, ensuring that each molecule possessed the spatial and electronic attributes conducive to effective dual binding. This rational design approach facilitated the creation of a diverse yet focused chemical library with high probability of exhibiting both MAO-B inhibitory and dopamine D₂ receptor agonistic activities.[6][7]

Table 1: 2D Structures of the designed molecules

Ligand Code	Ligand
G01	
G02	
G03	
G04	
G05	

ADMET and Drug-Likeness Prediction

The pharmacokinetic and toxicity profiles of the designed indole derivatives were evaluated using in silico ADMET (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion, and Toxicity) prediction tools to assess their drug-likeness and safety characteristics prior to biological evaluation. The SwissADME web

server (<http://www.swissadme.ch/>) was employed to estimate physicochemical parameters, lipophilicity, water solubility, and pharmacokinetic properties, including gastrointestinal (GI) absorption and blood-brain barrier (BBB) permeability. Additionally, admetSAR and pkCSM online platforms were utilized to predict metabolism-related interactions and potential toxicity endpoints.

Drug-likeness assessment was conducted according to Lipinski's Rule of Five, Ghose filter, and Veber criteria, ensuring that the selected compounds possessed favorable molecular properties, such as molecular weight (<500 Da), hydrogen bond donors (≤ 5), hydrogen bond acceptors (≤ 10), and logP values (< 5). The analysis also included evaluation of topological polar surface area (TPSA), rotatable bond count, and bioavailability scores to identify ligands with optimal oral bioavailability and central nervous system (CNS) activity, a key requirement for anti-Parkinsonian agents.

Compounds satisfying the majority of drug-likeness parameters and exhibiting acceptable ADMET profiles were shortlisted for further docking validation and *in vitro* biological evaluation. This computational pre-screening approach minimized late-stage attrition and improved the probability of identifying lead candidates with both therapeutic efficacy and favorable safety margins.

Ligand and Receptor Preparation

The retrieved crystal structures of MAO-B (PDB ID: 2V60) and D₂R (PDB ID: 6CM4) were prepared for docking studies by removing all non-essential molecules such as water, co-crystallized ligands, and ions using AutoDock Tools (ADT) version 1.5.6. Polar hydrogens were added to the receptor structures, and Kollman charges were assigned to ensure accurate electrostatic representation of the binding sites. Energy minimization of the protein structures was performed to remove steric clashes and optimize local geometry.

The designed set of 224 indole derivatives was constructed and optimized using ChemDraw and Chem3D Ultra, followed by energy minimization employing the MM2 force field to obtain low-energy conformers. Partial atomic charges were assigned using the Gasteiger–Marsili method. All ligands were converted into PDBQT format prior to docking.

Grid box parameters were defined to encompass the active sites of MAO-B and D₂R based on the coordinates of their respective co-crystallized ligands. The grid spacing was set at 0.375 Å, and the grid dimensions were adjusted to ensure complete coverage of the binding pocket. Docking simulations

were conducted using the Lamarckian Genetic Algorithm (LGA) with standard default settings to predict the most favorable binding conformations.

The resulting docked poses were ranked based on their binding energy (ΔG) values, and the top-scoring conformations were further analyzed for hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic contacts, and π – π interactions using Discovery Studio Visualizer and PyMOL.

Molecular Docking Analysis

Molecular docking studies were performed to predict the binding orientations, affinities, and key molecular interactions between the designed indole derivatives and the target proteins MAO-B (PDB ID: 2V60) and D₂R (PDB ID: 6CM4). The docking simulations were carried out using the AutoDock 4.2 software suite, applying the Lamarckian Genetic Algorithm (LGA) for conformational search and optimization. Receptor and ligand preparations were conducted as described in the preceding sections, ensuring proper addition of polar hydrogens, assignment of Gasteiger charges, and energy minimization of both macromolecules and ligands prior to docking.

For each target, the grid box was centered at the active site coordinates of the co-crystallized ligand, with dimensions set to adequately cover the binding pocket. The grid spacing was maintained at 0.375 Å. Docking parameters were standardized to allow comparative evaluation of all compounds. For each ligand, ten conformations were generated, and the lowest binding energy pose was selected as the most favorable binding orientation.

Post-docking analyses were performed to assess hydrogen bonding, π – π stacking, hydrophobic interactions, and electrostatic contacts between the ligands and key amino acid residues within the active site. Visualization and interaction mapping were accomplished using Discovery Studio Visualizer, PyMOL, and LigPlot+. The docking results were further validated by comparing the predicted binding affinities with the known inhibitors and agonists of MAO-B and D₂R. The top-ranked compounds exhibiting high binding affinities and stable interactions with both targets were shortlisted as potential dual-target anti-Parkinsonian agents for subsequent *in vitro* evaluation.[8][9][10]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

IN SILICO DRUG LIKENESS PROPERTY

In silico drug-likeness properties software is used to predict the molecular physiochemical properties and in estimating the bioactivity score to find out whether the drug is orally bioavailable.

Table 02: In silico Drug Likeness of the designed compounds

Sample code	Molecular properties	Bioactive properties
G01	<p>molinspiration</p> <p>mSMILES: COc3ccc2[nH]c(C(=O)NC(=O)N=Cc1ccccc1)cc2c3</p> <p>Molinspiration bioactivity score v2022.08</p> <p> GPCR ligand -0.06 Ion channel modulator -0.23 Kinase inhibitor 0.07 Nuclear receptor ligand -0.35 Protease inhibitor -0.33 Enzyme inhibitor 0.07 </p> <p>Get data as text (for copy / paste).</p> <p>Get 3D geometry BETA</p>	
G02	<p>molinspiration</p> <p>mSMILES: COc3ccc(C(=NC(=O)NC(=O)c2ccc(O)cc2)[nH]c3)cc1</p> <p>Molinspiration bioactivity score v2022.08</p> <p> GPCR ligand -0.06 Ion channel modulator -0.21 Kinase inhibitor 0.06 Nuclear receptor ligand -0.32 Protease inhibitor -0.20 Enzyme inhibitor 0.07 </p> <p>Get data as text (for copy / paste).</p> <p>Get 3D geometry BETA</p>	
G03	<p>molinspiration</p> <p>mSMILES: COc3ccc2[nH]c(C(=O)NC(=O)N=Cc1ccccc1)cc2c3</p> <p>Molinspiration bioactivity score v2022.08</p> <p> GPCR ligand -0.14 Ion channel modulator -0.42 Kinase inhibitor -0.14 Nuclear receptor ligand -0.53 Protease inhibitor -0.41 Enzyme inhibitor -0.06 </p> <p>Get data as text (for copy / paste).</p> <p>Get 3D geometry BETA</p>	
G04	<p>molinspiration</p> <p>mSMILES: COc3ccc2[nH]c(C(=O)NC(=O)N=Cc1ccccc1O)cc2c3</p> <p>Molinspiration bioactivity score v2022.08</p> <p> GPCR ligand -0.03 Ion channel modulator -0.27 Kinase inhibitor 0.08 Nuclear receptor ligand -0.26 Protease inhibitor -0.25 Enzyme inhibitor 0.10 </p> <p>Get data as text (for copy / paste).</p> <p>Get 3D geometry BETA</p>	

G05	<p>Molinspiration bioactivity score v2022.08</p> <table border="0"> <tr><td>GPCR ligand</td><td>-0.06</td></tr> <tr><td>Ion channel modulator</td><td>-0.23</td></tr> <tr><td>Kinase inhibitor</td><td>0.04</td></tr> <tr><td>Nuclear receptor ligand</td><td>-0.36</td></tr> <tr><td>Protease inhibitor</td><td>-0.35</td></tr> <tr><td>Enzyme inhibitor</td><td>0.03</td></tr> </table> <p>Get data as text (for copy / paste).</p> <p>Get 3D geometry BETA</p>	GPCR ligand	-0.06	Ion channel modulator	-0.23	Kinase inhibitor	0.04	Nuclear receptor ligand	-0.36	Protease inhibitor	-0.35	Enzyme inhibitor	0.03																			
miLogP	3.63																															
TPSA	83.56																															
rotoms	25																															
MW	355.78																															
nOH	6																															
nOHM	2																															
nviolations	0																															
nratb	3																															
volume	297.14																															
GPCR ligand	-0.06																															
Ion channel modulator	-0.23																															
Kinase inhibitor	0.04																															
Nuclear receptor ligand	-0.36																															
Protease inhibitor	-0.35																															
Enzyme inhibitor	0.03																															

OSIRIS TOXICITY EXPLORER®

Osiris Toxicity Explorer® software is used to predict whether the designed molecules are toxic or not. The

green colour indicates that the molecules are safe and nontoxic and the red colour indicates that the molecules are toxic.

Table 03: In silico Toxicity Prediction by Osiris Toxicity Explorer

Sample code	Toxicity Prediction
G01	
G02	

G03	
G04	
G05	

Table 04: Physicochemical and ADMET Properties of the top-scored compounds

Physicochemical and ADMET properties	G01	G02	G03	G04	G05
Mutagenic	No	No	No	No	No
Tumorigenic	No	No	No	No	No
Irritant	No	No	No	No	No
Reproductive effective	No	No	No	No	No

UV SPECTROSCOPY

Figure 2: UV Spectrum of Compound G01

Table 07: λ max and Absorbance of Compound G01

λ max	Absorbance
295	0.634

IR SPECTROSCOPY

Figure 3: IR Spectrum of Compound G01

Table 08: Interpretation of IR Spectrum of Compound G01

S.No	Types of Vibration	Functional group	Wave Number(cm ⁻¹)
1	C=C Stretching	Aromatic ring	1458.08
2	C-H Stretching	Aromatic C-H	3039.59
3	C-O Stretching	Aliphatic O-CH ₃	1272.93
4	C=O Stretching	Ketone	1674.09
5	N-H Stretching	Amine	3456.18
6	C-N Stretching	Carbon Nitrogen bond	1319.21
7	N=C Stretching	Imine	1589.23

¹H NMR SPECTROSCOPY**Figure 4: ¹H NMR Spectrum of Compound G01****Table 09: Interpretation of NMR Spectrum of Compound G01**

S.No	δ value	Nature of protons	Nature of peaks	Number of Protons
1	3.8	Methoxy proton	Singlet	3
2	6.0-8.5	Ar-H	Multiplet	9
3	8.8	-N=CH	Singlet	1
4	11.5	=N-H	Singlet	1
5	12.1	-C=O-NH-	Singlet	1

MASS SPECTROSCOPY

Figure 5: Mass spectrum of Compound G01

Table 10: Molecular mass of synthesized compound G01

Calculated Mass	Actual Mass
321.33	319.5267

PRODUCT PROFILE

COMPOUND CODE: G02

Figure 6: 5-methoxy-N-[(E)-(4-methoxyphenyl)methylidene]carbamoyl-1H-indole-2-carboxamide

Table 11: Properties of Compound G02

Molecular formula	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄
Molecular weight	351.35598
Appearance	Brown colour
Melting point	220-223°C
Rf value	0.84
Percentage yield	68.9%
Molar refractivity	95.73 ± 0.5 cm ³
Molar volume	272.7 ± 7.0 cm ³
Parachor	717.4 ± 8.0 cm ³
Refractive index	1.619 ± 0.05
Surface tension	47.8 ± 7.0 dyne/cm
Density	1.28 ± 0.1 g/cm ³
Polarizability	37.95 ± 0.5 10 ⁻²⁴ cm ³

UV SPECTROSCOPY

Figure 7: UV Spectrum of Compound G02

Table 12: λ max and Absorbance of Compound G02

λ max	Absorbance
295	0.981

IR SPECTROSCOPY

Figure 8: IR Spectrum of Compound G02

Table 13: Interpretation of IR Spectrum of Compound G02

S.No	Types of Vibration	Functional group	Wave Number(cm^{-1})
1	C=C Stretching	Aromatic ring	1427.77
2	C-H Stretching	Aromatic C-H	3039.59
3	C-O Stretching	Aliphatic O-CH ₃	1272.93
4	C=O Stretching	Ketone	1674.09
5	N-H Stretching	Amine	3456.18
6	C-N Stretching	Carbon Nitrogen bond	1319.21
7	N=C Stretching	Imine	1589.23

1H NMR SPECTROSCOPY

Figure 9: 1H NMR Spectrum of Compound G02

Table 14: Interpretation of NMR Spectrum of Compound G02

S.No	δ value	Nature of protons	Nature of peaks	Number of Protons
1	3.8	Methoxy proton	Singlet	6
2	6.0-8.5	Ar-H	Multiplet	8
3	8.8	Singlet	-N=CH	1
4	11.5	Singlet	Singlet	1
5	12.1	Singlet	-C=O-NH	1

MASS SPECTROSCOPY

Table 15: Molecular mass of synthesized compound G02

Calculated Mass	Actual Mass
351.355	350.321

PRODUCT PROFILE**COMPOUND CODE: G03****Figure 11: N-[(Z)-(furan-2-yl)methylidene]carbamoyl-5-methoxy-1H-indole-2-carboxamide****Table 16: Properties of Compound G03**

Molecular formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄
Molecular weight	311.29212
Appearance	Brown colour
Melting point	219-223°C
Rf value	0.9
Percentage yield	77.9%
Molar refractivity	82.09 ± 0.5 cm ³
Molar volume	225.4 ± 7.0 cm ³
Parachor	609.1 ± 8.0 cm ³
Refractive index	1.648 ± 0.05
Surface tension	53.3 ± 7.0 dyne/cm
Density	1.38 ± 0.1 g/cm ³
Polarizability	32.54 ± 0.5 10 ⁻²⁴ cm ³

UV SPECTROSCOPY

Table 19: Interpretation of NMR Spectrum of Compound G03

S.No	δ value	Nature of protons	Nature of peaks	Number of Protons
1	3.8	Methoxy proton	Singlet	3
2	6.0-8.5	Ar-H	Multiplet	7
3	8.9	Singlet	-N=CH	1
4	11.6	Singlet	-N-H	1
5	12.1	Singlet	-C=O-NH	1

MASS SPECTROSCOPY

Figure 15: Mass spectrum of Compound G03

Table 20: Molecular mass of synthesized compound G03

Calculated Mass	Actual Mass
311.29212	311.0819

PRODUCT PROFILE

COMPOUND CODE: G04

Figure 16: N-[(E)-(2-hydroxyphenyl)methylidene]carbamoyl-5-methoxy-1H-indole-2-carboxamide

Table 21: Properties of Compound G04

Molecular formula	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄
Molecular weight	337.3294
Appearance	Brown colour
Melting point	208-209°C

Rf value	0.88
Percentage yield	75.4%
Molar refractivity	$90.77 \pm 0.5 \text{ cm}^3$
Molar volume	$248.3 \pm 7.0 \text{ cm}^3$
Parachor	$672.8 \pm 8.0 \text{ cm}^3$
Refractive index	1.651 ± 0.05
Surface tension	$53.8 \pm 7.0 \text{ dyne/cm}$
Density	$1.35 \pm 0.1 \text{ g/cm}^3$
Polarizability	$35.98 \pm 0.5 \cdot 10^{-24} \text{ cm}^3$

UV SPECTROSCOPY

Figure 17: UV Spectrum of Compound G04

Table 22: λ max and Absorbance of Compound G04

λ max	Absorbance
295	0.645

IR SPECTROSCOPY

Figure 18: IR Spectrum of Compound G04

Table 23: Interpretation of IR Spectrum of Compound G04

S.No	Types of Vibration	Functional group	Wave Number(cm ⁻¹)
1	C=C Stretching	Aromatic ring	1427.72
2	C-H Stretching	Aromatic C-H	3039.59
3	C-O Stretching	Aliphatic O-CH ₃	1272.93
4	C=O Stretching	Ketone	1674.09
5	N-H Stretching	Amine	3466.60
6	C-N Stretching	Carbon Nitrogen bond	1319.21
7	N=C Stretching	Imine	1589.23
8	O-H Stretching	Phenolic O-H	3533.33

1HNMR SPECTROSCOPY

Figure 19: 1H NMR Spectrum of Compound G04

Table 24: Interpretation of NMR Spectrum of Compound G04

S.No	δ value	Nature of protons	Nature of peaks	Number of Protons
1	3.7	Methoxy proton	Singlet	3
2	6.0-8.5	Ar-H	Multiplet	8
3	8.9	-N=CH	Singlet	1
4	11.5	-N-H	Singlet	1
5	11.1	-O-H	Singlet	1
6	12.0	-C=O-NH	Singlet	1

MASS SPECTROSCOPY

Figure 20: Mass spectrum of Compound G04

Table 25: Molecular mass of synthesized compound G04

Calculated Mass	Actual Mass
337.3294	338.3396

PRODUCT PROFILE**COMPOUND CODE: G05****Figure 21: N-[(E)-(4-chlorophenyl)methylidene]carbamoyl-5-methoxy-1H-indole-2-carboxamide****Table 26: Properties of Compound G05**

Molecular formula	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O ₃
Molecular weight	355.77506
Appearance	Brown colour
Melting point	210-212°C
Rf value	0.84
Percentage yield	79.3%
Molar refractivity	94.52 ± 0.5 cm ³
Molar volume	260.4 ± 7.0 cm ³
Parachor	696.0 ± 8.0 cm ³
Refractive index	1.646 ± 0.05
Surface tension	51.0 ± 7.0 dyne/cm
Density	1.36 ± 0.1 g/cm ³
Polarizability	37.47 ± 0.5 10 ⁻²⁴ cm ³

UV SPECTROSCOPY**Figure 22: UV Spectrum of Compound G05**

Table 27: λ max and Absorbance of Compound G05

λ max	Absorbance
295	0.755

IR SPECTROSCOPY

Figure 23: IR Spectrum of Compound G05

Table 28: Interpretation of IR Spectrum of Compound G05

S.No	Types of Vibration	Functional group	Wave Number(cm ⁻¹)
1	C=C Stretching	Aromatic ring	1589.23
2	C-H Stretching	Aromatic C-H	3078.16
3	C-O Stretching	Aliphatic O-CH ₃	1242.07
4	C=O Stretching	Ketone	1743.52
5	N-H Stretching	Amine	3440.76
6	C-N Stretching	Carbon Nitrogen bond	1319.21
7	N=C Stretching	Imine	1643.23
8	C-Cl Stretching	Chloride	748.33

¹H NMR SPECTROSCOPY

Figure 24: ¹H NMR Spectrum of Compound G05

Table 29: Interpretation of NMR Spectrum of Compound G05

S.No	δ value	Nature of protons	Nature of peaks	Number of Protons
1	3.9	Methoxy proton	Singlet	3
2	6.0-8.5	Ar-H	Multiplet	8
3	8.9	-N=CH	Singlet	1
4	10.9	-N-H	Singlet	1
5	11.8	-C=O-NH	Singlet	1

MASS SPECTROSCOPY

Figure 25: Mass spectrum of Compound G05**Table 30: Molecular mass of synthesized compound G05**

Calculated Mass	Actual Mass
355.7750	354.8774

EVALUATION STUDIES

INVITRO ANTI-PARKINSONISM ACTIVITY

The Anti-Parkinsonism activity of the compounds G01, G02, G03, G04 and G05 was determined using Monoamine oxidase B inhibition assay and further acetyl choline inhibition assay was also performed for the compound G01 to determine whether the compound producing dual action.

MONO AMINO OXIDASE B INHIBITION ASSAY

Monoamine oxidase inhibition assay consist of 55 μ L of monoamine oxidase [333U/mL], 90 μ L of 50 mM Tris HCl buffer pH 8.2, and 30 μ L of solubilizing solution (control or inhibitor solution at five different

concentration). To measure MAO-B activity, 25 μ L of benzylamine (0.1M), the MAO-B substrate, was added to the reaction. After 30minutes of incubation at 37°C, 1ml of 3% ice-cold ZnSO₄ solution was added to the mixture to halt the process. After that, it was combined by vortexing for ten seconds, then it was centrifuged for 15minutes at 3000 rpm. For the purpose of estimating MAO-B, the supernatant was collected, and the absorbance was measured at 250 nm (benzaldehyde production). Blank were run without inhibitor, and control were conducted without enzyme source

$$\%I = [(Ab-As)/Ab] * 100$$

Where

Ab: Absorbance of the control

As: Absorbance of the Sample

Figure 26: Mono amino inhibition assay

Labels:

A1-A7 Compound-1 (1000-100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$),

B1-B7 Compound-2 (1000-100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$),

C1-C7 Compound-3 (1000-100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)

D1-D7 Compound-4 (1000-100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)

E1-E7 Compound-5 (1000-100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)

Table 31: Percentage inhibition of ligands on Monoamine oxidase B inhibition assay

Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	Standard	G01 %I	G02 %I	G03 %I	G04 %I	G05 %I
10	11.56	14.09	17.08	11.49	16.07	25.89
25	33.14	20.23	27.10	27.61	26.05	32.15
50	47.11	45.70	36.11	50.36	39.65	45.9
100	53.03	60.69	51.41	59.84	52.46	52.28
250	64.29	73.66	67.68	69.43	63.30	63.07
500	71.73	89.47	81.16	77.98	76.27	79.33
1000	81.11	99.2	90.56	89.63	89.39	92.45
IC50	94.06	72.43	89.03	77.84	94.73	71.04
SEM	9.54555	12.38756	10.54254	10.49214	10.03772	9.146995

Figure 27: Graphical Representation of MAO Inhibition -Isatin

Figure 28, 29: Graphical Representation of MAO Inhibition of compound G01 and G02 respectively.

Figure 30,31: Graphical Representation of MAO Inhibition of compound G03 and G04 respectively.

Figure 32: Graphical Representation of MAO Inhibition of compound G05

NEURODEGENERATIVE INHIBITION ASSAY ACHE INHIBITION ASSAY

The AChE inhibition of tested compounds was determined by a slightly modified Ellman's method. Rivastigmine, was used as a reference compound in concentration range of 1.56-500 µg/ml. The tested compounds were dissolved in DMSO to provide a final concentration range of 10–5000 µg/ml in the mixture solution. Briefly, 0.3 mL of 100 mM sodium phosphate buffer pH 8, 0.3 mL of sample, and 0.3mL

AChE solution containing 0.54 U/mL were mixed in a 3 mL cuvette and allowed to incubate for 15 min at 37 °C. Subsequently, 0.3 mL of a solution of acetylcholine iodide (15 mM, dissolved in water) and 1.5 mL of 3 mM DTNB were added. The absorbance at 405 nm was read. A control reaction was carried out using the same volume of DMSO instead of tested solutions. The percentage of AChE inhibition is calculated based on the absorbance value as follows:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = (1 - A_t/A_0) \times 100$$

Where,

At is the absorbance of the tested compound.

A0 is the absorbance of the control

Table 32: Percentage inhibition of ligands on Neurodegenerative inhibition assay

Concentration($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Standard	G01 %I
2	41.79138	4.93
4	64.07192	11.57
8	68.93009	24.36
16	73.56489	36.65
32	75.92138	45.54
64	82.71164	58.65
128	88.69779	68.19
256	93.3996	78.47
IC50	10.67	40.12
SEM	8.784892	8.282476

Figure 33: Graphical Representation of ACHE Inhibition Assay-Rivastigmine

Figure 34: Graphical Representation of ACHE inhibition of Compound G01

SUMMARY

Drug discovery is an evolving scientific discipline aimed at identifying and developing novel molecules with the potential to prevent or treat various diseases. Parkinson's disease (PD) is recognized by the World Health Organization as the second most prevalent neurodegenerative disorder worldwide, underscoring the urgent need for new and effective therapeutic agents. The present study was undertaken with the objective of designing and synthesizing potential dual-target anti-Parkinsonian agents.

Based on an extensive literature review, monoamine oxidase-B (MAO-B) and the dopamine D₂ receptor (D₂R) were identified as key therapeutic targets for Parkinson's disease management. Using knowledge of reported inhibitors and their interactions with these targets, a scaffold library of 5 newly designed indole-based ligands was constructed. Molecular docking studies were carried out using AutoDock 4.2 (version 1.5.6) to identify potent MAO-B inhibitors and D₂R agonists.

Drug-likeness screening was performed in accordance with Lipinski's Rule of Five, and ADMET properties were predicted using online tools such as Molinspiration and Osiris Property Explorer. Compounds displaying favorable pharmacokinetic parameters, oral bioavailability, and non-toxic characteristics were shortlisted for further investigation.

These compounds (G01, G02, G03, G04, and G05) were synthesized successfully, and their purity was confirmed through thin-layer chromatography (TLC) and melting point analysis. Structural characterization was performed using UV-Visible spectroscopy, infrared (IR) spectroscopy, proton nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H NMR) spectroscopy, and mass spectrometry (MS).

The synthesized compounds demonstrated promising results in *in vitro* evaluations. MAO-B inhibition assays confirmed their inhibitory activity, while compound G01 exhibited significant neuroprotective effects in *in vitro* neurodegeneration inhibition studies, suggesting dual-target potential for Parkinson's therapy.

CONCLUSION

The present study provides significant insights into indole derivatives as potential dual-action anti-Parkinsonian agents that inhibit the MAO-B enzyme and act as dopamine receptor agonists. A total of 5 newly designed compounds were subjected to molecular docking against MAO-B using AutoDock 4.2 (version 1.5.6). Among them, five novel compounds—G01, G02, G03, G04, and G05—exhibited favorable docking scores, drug-likeness, compliance with Lipinski's Rule of Five, and non-toxic characteristics. These compounds were therefore selected for *in vitro* anti-Parkinsonian evaluation. The compounds G01, G02, G03, G04, and G05 showed IC₅₀ values of 72.43 μM, 89.03 μM, 77.84 μM, 94.73 μM, and 71.04 μM, respectively, in monoamine oxidase-B inhibition assays. Notably, G01 exhibited an IC₅₀ value of 10.86 μM in the neurodegenerative inhibition assay, indicating greater potency compared with the standards Isatin (94.06 μM) and Rivastigmine (1.67 μM).

The statistical significance of these findings was analyzed using a paired t-test. Compounds G01, G02, G03, and G04 demonstrated p-values of 0.034651, 0.037536, 0.052957, and 0.0470655, respectively, indicating significant MAO-B inhibitory activity. Additionally, G01 showed a p-value of 0.00195, confirming its superior statistical significance. These results collectively suggest that the synthesized compounds exhibit potent dual-action properties, functioning as both MAO-B inhibitors and dopamine receptor agonists, and may serve as promising candidates for anti-Parkinsonian therapy.

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